

**LOCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE MAIN NETWORKS
OF WORLD TRANSPORT.**

Davlatkhon Karimovna Muqimova¹

¹PhD in Technicals, Department of On Land Transport systems,
Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

(*Corresponding author's e-mail: davl.kosi@mail.ru)

Furqatbek Shuhratbek O'g'li Dumahonov²

²Senior Lecturer, Department of On Land Transport systems,
Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

Boburjon Zoyirjon O'g'li Zokirov³

(**Corresponding author's e-mail: dariyod@bk.ru)

³Student, Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

Javohirbek Tohirjon O'g'li Rahmonjonov⁴

⁴Student, Andijan Machine-Building Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7181916>

There is a good reason to call automobile transport the transport of the 20th century. It was created at the beginning of our century and now the car has become an integral part of our life. The length of the roads is increasing, 24 mln. km. reached About half of it belongs to five countries - USA, India, Russia, Japan and China. Automobiliation has reached an all-time high in the United States. Here, on average, there are 600 cars per thousand people. In many countries of Western Europe, this indicator is somewhat higher: 300-400 and even more.[1].

Features of foreign economic relations and main forms of international economic relations in countries at different stages of socio-economic development. Foreign economic relations are a consequence of the international geographical division of labor. The emergence and development of the division of labor between countries is an objective law of social production, an important factor in the forward movement of individual society. As social production developed, the division of labor gradually moved beyond the national boundaries of some countries. As a result, the international division of labor, and the world market on its basis, appeared.

The countries of the world are at different stages of socio-economic development, and foreign economic relations are equally necessary for all of them. Any powerful country (USA, Japan, GFR, etc.) and a developing country are very dependent on product exchange and trade. Because economically developed countries feel the need for raw materials, ready industrial products are very necessary for developing countries. Socio-economically highly developed countries have various economic relations with the countries of the world. The share of foreign economic relations in their gross domestic product is increasing. They will have a large foreign currency

income due to the fact that they produce ready-made goods, especially the most modern products (engineering and chemical industry products). They also get a lot of profit by exporting capital abroad and giving loans.[2,3].

Socio-economically less developed or developing countries export and sell raw materials and semi-finished products (cotton fiber, coffee, tea, sugar, etc.) and bring their own finished industrial products. As a result, their foreign trade indicator often has a negative balance.

Since the end of the 80s, the "Cold War" period has ended in the world, and integration processes have begun to intensify. The scope of foreign economic relations between the countries of the world has expanded and various forms of foreign economic relations have begun to appear.

The following main forms of foreign economic relations can be distinguished according to their functional characteristics:

1. Foreign trade. This form of foreign economic relations is relevant for all countries of the world and consists of product exchange, sale and purchase. The developing countries cannot produce or grow all the necessary industrial and agricultural products by themselves. That's why they buy the products they need and buy the products they need. Some countries import some products because it is cheaper to import them than to produce them. For example, the US imports iron ore, non-ferrous metals, and oil.
2. Finance-credit relations. Economically developed countries can have huge benefits through relations with many countries of the world, especially developing countries, such as giving loans, starting banking operations, issuing securities, and buying their shares. Especially in this way, the companies and banks of USA, Japan, GFR, Switzerland, Great Britain are getting huge funds.
3. Scientific and technical cooperation. Many countries in the world exchange various scientific and technical information, sell licenses giving the right to manufacture various machines and equipment, exchange patents, etc. The developed countries of the world are cooperating in the development of space, creation of new techniques and technologies.
4. Provision of various services or "invisible export". This type of XIAs is developing very quickly. Countries of the world also benefit economically by providing services to foreign ships entering their ports, planes landing at their airports, and transit vehicles.
5. Financing and joint construction of large public economic facilities. Companies from different countries cooperate in building plants and factories, dams,

reservoirs, bridges, hotels and roads. After completing the work according to the specified share, the profit will be shared accordingly.

6. International tourism. Interstate exchange of tourists has become a lucrative industry for some countries. 550 million worldwide. more than 2000 tourists participate in various trips. Countries such as Spain, France, Italy, Greece, Switzerland earn a lot of income from international tourism.[4,5,6].

Foreign economic relations between the countries of the world. The international geographical division of labor is based on increasing the efficiency of economic management of people as much as possible, providing them with various products offered on the world market. Among the countries of the world, specialization is increasing not only in the production of ready-made products, but also in the production of details and semi-finished products. Countries of the world began to pay more attention to quality, not quantity.

Because of this, 60% of the world trade turnover is accounted for by mutual trade between the economically developed countries of the West. Mature integration relations have been formed between them.

Foreign economic relations of the current world are becoming very diverse.

One of the main characteristics of the current stage of world economic development is the faster growth of international trade relations than the production of industrial products.[7,8].

In 1995, the amount of export of goods around the world was 4875 billion. to dollars, export of services is 1230 bln. was equal to one dollar. 25 leading countries account for 85.3% of world exports and 83.8% of imports. In some of them, these indicators are as follows: USA-15.5 and 19.9%, Germany-11.6 and 10.7%, Japan-11.8 and 8.6%, France-6 and 6.3%, Great Britain-5.2 and 5.8%.

8.5% of the world's exports go to the rapidly developing new industrial countries of South-East Asia, and 10% to the oil-exporting countries (members of the OPEC organization).[9,10].

Despite the fact that the process of attracting national economies to the international trade system is accelerating, the world commodity circulation is characterized by high territorial concentration. For example, the five largest exporting countries account for almost half of the world's trade turnover.

It is worth noting that, despite the decreasing weight of the flow of basic goods in the general circulation of goods, relations between neighboring countries prevail. 9 out of 15 main interstate cooperations in the world correspond to neighboring countries. For example, USA-Canada, Germany-France, Netherlands-Belgium, etc. This is connected with the characteristics of the integration

movements between the economically developed countries and the uniformity of their multi-sectoral complex economies. On the contrary, the economy of many developing countries is based on natural resources, which does not allow exchange of products between neighboring countries. Because the natural conditions and natural resources of the neighboring countries are almost the same. Those belonging to the core group of developing countries and the group of newly industrialized countries are rapidly entering the world stage. For example, the weight of the countries located in the eastern part of the Pacific Ocean in the world's gross product production doubled in the next 20 years, the gross share of the world's exports of the 4 newly industrialized countries (South Korea, Taiwan, Syangang, Singapore) increased 4 times and amounted to 14%.

The world export of goods in 1950 was 0.35 trillion. equal to the dollar, in 1970 - 1.25, in 1980 - 2.25, in 1990 - 3.48 and in 1997 - 5.4 trillion. amounted to dollars (in 1990 prices).

Thus, in 40 years, the volume of world trade increased 10 times. The most important aspect of the world trade turnover was the changes in the structure of goods under the influence of geographical division of labor and scientific and technical progress. That is, the weight of fuel, raw materials, and food products is decreasing, and the weight of the products of fantalab production industries is increasing. This can also be seen from the following table:

These changes took place in connection with the sharp decrease in the dependence of the economically developed countries of the West on the import of raw materials from the developing countries.

Changes in the structure of world trade (in %)

Product groups	1960	1970	1980	1990	1995	2006
Raw materials and food	55	50	47	25	24	25
Finished products	45	50	53	75	76	75

For many countries of the world, international trade remains the main form of foreign economic relations. The level of involvement in the international division of labor depends on the level of development of the productive forces. Due to this, industrialized countries occupy leading positions in international trade, specializing in the delivery of high-tech products (machines, electronic equipment, pharmaceuticals and fine chemical products) [9-10].

To determine the degree of attraction of a country to the world economy, the export quota of the economy is used (an indicator determined by the ratio of the amount of exports of goods and services to the gross domestic product).

1975-1995 yillari mobaynida eksport kvotasi 12% dan 22% gacha, tovarlar eksporti bo'yicha (yoqilg'ilarsiz) 8% dan 13% gacha, xizmatlar eksporti bo'yicha 1,5% dan 3,0% gacha usdi.

During 1975-1995, the export quota increased from 12% to 22%, the export of goods (excluding fuels) from 8% to 13%, and the export of services from 1.5% to 3.0%.

The weight of machine-building products, cars, electronic equipment, chemical products, textile products, processed wood, and paper products has increased in world exports. The weight of non-ferrous metals, steel, food products decreased. More than 20% of the products and services produced in the world come to the world market.

Since the size of the domestic market in most of the developing countries is not large, and export specialization consists of a few products, it makes their farms very dependent on the fluctuating prices in the world market, forming monoculture (single governance) specialization in them.

References:

1. L.Y.Bakirov M.A.Nurdinov Avtomobillarda xalqaro yuk tashish qoidalari. T. 2021 370 bet.
2. Международное руководство по безопасному креплению груза на автомобильном транспорте. IRU_CIT-2014-74с.
- 3.Топалиди В.А., Чубенко Н.М., «Международные автомобильные перевозки грузов» Учебное пособие. Ташкент 2017-339с
- 4.Курганов В.М., Миротин Л.Б., «Международные грузовые автомобильное перевозки» Учебное пособие для вузов. Тверь, 2000-131с.
5. Muqimova D., Nurdinov M. COMPLIANCE WITH RESPONSIBILITY AND WORK REGIMES OF DRIVERS IN LEGAL REGULATORY DOCUMENTS DUE TO ACCIDENTS IN THE TRANSPORTATION OF INTERNATIONAL GOODS BY TRUCKS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 15-25.
6. Shukurov M. M. et al. Roads, road lines and thermoplastic products used in their drawing //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 258-263.
7. Shukurov M. et al. Highways, Functions And Importance //The American Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 04. – С. 1-6.

8. Samatov, G. A., and Giyasidinov A. Sh. "Increasing the export potential of fruit and vegetable products in Uzbekistan and simplifying the procedure for its transportation." International Engineering Journal For Research & Development 5.3 (2020).

9. Икромов Н. А., Гиясидинов А. Ш., Рузиматов Б. Р. У. Меры по снижению экологического воздействия автопарка //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 4-1 (85). – С. 44-47.

10. Xushnud Rahmonov, Xayrullo Odilov ORGANIZATION OF QUALITY TRANSPORT SERVICE - Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research

ISSN: 2278-4853 Vol. 11, Issue 5, May 2022 DOI: 10.5958/2278-4853.2022.00122.7

